

Ground Subsidence Impact on High-Speed Rail Track Irregularity

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ABSTRACT: A parallel between track irregularities and ground subsidence is established in this paper through a common parameter, curvature. The curvature of the ground surface caused by differential subsidence is obtained from the second derivative of the displacement solution developed by Mindlin and Chang for a spherical inclusion in an elastic half-space. The allowable track irregularity specified by the Federal Railroad Administration (FRA), defined as the maximum deviation of the rail surface from a uniform profile measured at the mid-ordinate of a 62-foot chord, is converted into an equivalent curvature. By bridging these two domains through curvature, an explicit expression is derived relating track irregularity to the size and depth of an unevenly distributed volume of consolidating soil. The volumetric shrinkage of a subsurface soil inclusion produces differential subsidence at the ground surface, which introduces additional track irregularity. The analysis shows that the resulting ground-surface curvature is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the inclusion depth, indicating rapid decay with increasing depth. Consequently, the impact of subsurface soil consolidation on track irregularity becomes negligible when the consolidating layer is sufficiently deep.

KEYWORDS: Subsidence, Track Irregularity, Nuclei of Strain, Half-Space Elasticity, High-Speed Rail, Galerkin Vector, Soil Consolidation.

SITE LOCATION: [Geographic Database](#)

(requires Google Earth) **No need to write anything here, but the coordinates of the project will need to be provided to add in the Google Earth Database.**

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INTRODUCTION

High-speed rail systems proposed in regions affected by long-term groundwater extraction may traverse areas where significant ground subsidence has occurred over many decades. To evaluate the potential impacts of subsidence on the design and operation of high-speed rail infrastructure, including civil structures, track systems, and operational safety, previous studies of subsidence-prone regions have documented two key observations:

- In some locations, the annual subsidence rate can reach values on the order of 1.5 ft per year near transportation corridors.
- Despite the magnitude of cumulative settlement, the gradients (slopes) and curvatures (rates of change of gradient) of the ground-surface profile typically remain relatively gentle over large spatial scales when evaluated across historical records spanning multiple decades.

While the first observation appears alarming, this paper focuses on the second: the consistently gentle curvature of the subsidence profile. For railway systems, it is not the magnitude of the vertical profile change itself that governs track

42 performance, but rather the curvature of the profile, which determines the level of track irregularity and its impact on the
43 safety and comfort of high-speed train operation.

44 It is intuitive that a shrinking (or expanding) subsurface volume produces deformation of the ground surface, and that the
45 magnitude of this deformation depends on the size and depth of the source. A closed-form solution to this problem was
46 developed by Mindlin and Chang, based on the theory of nuclei of strain in an elastic half-space and expressed in terms of
47 the Galerkin vector. In this paper, the curvature of the ground-surface deformation is obtained from the second derivative of
48 the Mindlin and Chang displacement solution.

49 On the railway side, the Federal Railroad Administration (FRA) Track Safety Standards Compliance Manual specifies the
50 allowable vertical track irregularity as the maximum deviation of the rail surface from a uniform profile measured at the mid-
51 ordinate of a 62-foot chord. This allowable deviation can be converted into an equivalent curvature and used as the allowable
52 curvature threshold for subsidence-induced deformation.

53 The analysis shows that the curvature of the ground surface is inversely proportional to the fourth power of the depth of the
54 subsurface inclusion. As a result, the induced curvature decays rapidly with increasing depth, indicating that the impact of
55 differential subsidence on track irregularity becomes negligible when the consolidating soil layer is sufficiently deep.

56 **TRACK IRREGULARITY AND THE CURVATURE OF THE PROFILE CHANGE**

57 Track irregularities include vertical irregularity, horizontal irregularity, gauge irregularity, and twisting irregularity (the
58 geometric difference between the two rails). In this paper, only subsidence-induced vertical track irregularity is considered.

59 When train wheels pass through a region with track irregularity, an acceleration is generated at the wheel–rail interface due
60 to the curvature of the vertical profile change associated with the irregularity. This acceleration is subsequently amplified
61 through the multi-rigid-body dynamic system consisting of the vehicle body, bogies, wheelsets, suspension springs, and
62 dampers. The resulting dynamic amplification factor is sensitive to the wavelength of the profile curvature. In general, longer
63 wavelengths produce smaller dynamic amplification effects.

64 Track-geometry irregularities are commonly classified into three wavelength ranges: short wavelength (1 mm–3.5 m), mainly
65 caused by periodic variations in track material properties during rail rolling and by periodic wheel–rail wear; medium
66 wavelength (3 m–30 m); and long wavelength (30 m–100 m), typically associated with uneven residual settlement of the
67 embankment. Subsidence-induced track irregularity generally falls within the long-wavelength range and beyond.

68 For Class 9 track (operating speeds exceeding 200 mph), the Federal Railroad Administration (FRA) specifies the allowable
69 vertical track irregularity as a maximum track surface deviation of $\frac{3}{4}$ in. measured at the mid-ordinate of a 62-foot chord. In
70 this paper, this allowable deviation is converted into an equivalent curvature, which is adopted as the allowable curvature
71 threshold for differential subsidence (Fig. 1).

$$\hat{k} = 1/R = 8\delta/L^2 = 1/7688 \text{ (1/ft)}$$

72

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Figure 1. Track surface deviation vs. equivalent curvature

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If the curvature induced by differential subsidence remains below this threshold, the resulting track irregularity will remain within the allowable tolerances specified by FRA standards.

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Soil is a composite material consisting of solid grains and void spaces. The behavior of soil under environmental changes is strongly influenced by the contents of these voids. Depending on the degree of water saturation, soil can be categorized into three conditions:

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- Saturated soil – the void spaces are completely filled with water. This condition typically occurs below the groundwater table, where hydrostatic pressure maintains full saturation.
- Unsaturated soil – the voids are partially filled with water and partially filled with air. This condition generally exists above the groundwater table and represents a transitional state between saturated and dry soil.
- Dry soil – the void spaces are filled entirely with air with negligible water content, typically occurring near the ground surface in arid environments or during prolonged dry periods.

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The transition from saturated to unsaturated, and eventually to dry soil, occurs gradually along the vertical soil profile and is influenced by capillary effects, evapotranspiration, and negative pore-water pressure above the groundwater table.

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A conceptual representation of soil behavior can be illustrated using a free-body diagram of a soil block bounded by the ground surface at the top and a hypothetical curved surface at the bottom representing the contact points between soil grains (Fig. 2). The equilibrium of this soil block is governed by the balance between the self-weight of the soil mass acting downward and the combined resistance of grain-contact forces and pore-water pressure acting upward. When groundwater is withdrawn, the pore-water pressure decreases while the soil self-weight remains essentially unchanged. According to Terzaghi's effective stress principle, this reduction in pore pressure increases the effective stress acting at the grain contacts, which compresses the soil skeleton and reduces the void volume. The resulting consolidation leads to a reduction in soil layer thickness and produces ground subsidence.

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Figure 2. Free body diagram for effective stress

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99 In the study of ground subsidence, a fundamental concept is the equilibrium of a soil mass. This equilibrium is maintained
100 by the balance between the self-weight of the soil layers acting downward and the upward resistance provided by grain-
101 contact reactions and pore-water pressure within the void spaces. This system can be represented by a free-body diagram of
102 a soil block, assuming friction-free lateral boundaries for the case of soil uniformly distributed in the horizontal directions.

103 Terzaghi introduced the concept of effective stress to describe the stress transmitted through soil-grain contacts,
104 distinguishing it from the total stress, which includes both grain-contact stress and pore-water pressure.

105 **TRACK IRREGULARITY AND THE CURVATURE OF THE PROFILE CHANGE**

106 Groundwater dynamics play a critical role in subsidence phenomena. A decline in the groundwater table reduces the pore-
107 water pressure within the soil voids, thereby transferring a greater portion of the vertical load to the soil-grain contact points.
108 This increase in grain-contact stress compresses the soil skeleton, reduces the void volume, and results in ground subsidence.

109 Although changes in groundwater levels also alter the distribution of saturated, unsaturated, and dry soil layers, the resulting
110 change in soil self-weight is relatively small compared with the reduction in pore pressure and is commonly neglected in
111 geotechnical analysis. Consequently, when the groundwater table drops, the soil self-weight remains essentially unchanged
112 while pore pressure decreases, leading to an increase in effective stress.

113 According to Terzaghi's theory of soil consolidation, the relationship between void ratio and effective stress follows a
114 characteristic loading path during consolidation (Fig. 3). As effective stress increases, the void ratio decreases, representing
115 compression of the soil skeleton. During unloading, when effective stress decreases due to reduced overburden or recovery
116 of groundwater levels, the soil follows a flatter rebound path. Upon reloading, the stress–void ratio path retraces the rebound
117 curve until reaching the previous maximum effective stress, beyond which consolidation resumes.

Figure 3. Terzaghi theory of soil consolidation

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120 Subsidence can be induced by several mechanisms, including groundwater extraction, hydrocompaction, oil and gas
121 extraction, tectonic subsidence, and the compression of organic soils and peat. The subsidence observed in the California
122 High-Speed Rail CP2–3 construction package near Tulare Lake is primarily caused by groundwater extraction and follows
123 the mechanism described by Terzaghi’s consolidation theory. Due to the deep groundwater table and repeated cycles of
124 drought-driven groundwater depletion in the region’s alluvial deposits, the consolidating soil layers responsible for
125 subsidence are located well below the embankment foundation and pile tips. Consequently, the subsidence does not
126 significantly affect geotechnical design considerations such as pile downdrag or reduction in foundation bearing capacity.

127 **HALF-SPACE ASYMMETRIC ELASTICITY PROBLEM**

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129 A uniform drop in the groundwater table within soil of uniform properties produces uniform consolidation, resulting in a
130 uniform change in void ratio Δe and a corresponding uniform ground subsidence ΔD (Fig. 4).

131 Uniform subsidence does not introduce track irregularity. In practice, however, soil properties and the distribution of aquifers
132 and aquitards are rarely uniform, and groundwater withdrawal is spatially uneven. These conditions produce differential
133 consolidation, which leads to differential subsidence at the ground surface.

134 To represent an upper-bound case of differential subsidence, the consolidating soil is idealized as a volume of shrinking
135 material embedded within a non-consolidating elastic medium (Fig. 5). The analytical solution to this problem was developed
136 by Mindlin and Chang, based on the theory of nuclei of strain in an elastic half-space.

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Figure 4. Uniform ground subsidence

Figure 5. Half-space elasticity with an inclusion

140 The volumetric expansion (or shrinkage) rate of the soil inclusion is defined as $\beta = \frac{\delta V}{V}$

141 where V is the original volume of the inclusion and δV is the change in volume.

142 For a spherical inclusion, the volumetric strain can be expressed in terms of the linear expansion ratio

$$143 \quad \alpha = \frac{\delta a}{a}$$

144 where a is the radius of the inclusion and δa is the change in radius. The relationship between volumetric and linear strain is

$$145 \quad \beta = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^3$$

146 and, neglecting higher-order terms,

$$147 \quad \beta \approx 3\alpha$$

148 In soil mechanics, volumetric strain is commonly expressed in terms of void ratio e , giving

$$149 \quad \beta = \frac{\Delta e}{1 + e_0}$$

150 where e_0 is the initial void ratio prior to consolidation.

151 MINDLIN AND CHANG SOLUTION

152 The displacement field generated by a volumetric strain source in an elastic medium can be analyzed using the nuclei of strain
153 formulation. The classical solution for a concentrated force applied within an infinite elastic body was first derived by Kelvin.
154 Mindlin later extended this formulation to include additional singularities such as double forces, centers of dilatation, and
155 doublets, collectively referred to as nuclei of strain, a term originally introduced by Love.

156 These nuclei of strain form a set of fundamental solutions that can be superimposed to construct displacement fields
157 corresponding to more complex loading conditions. In particular, they allow localized volumetric strain sources to be
158 represented analytically within elastic media.

159 Mindlin and Cheng applied this concept to the case of a half-space elasticity problem, introducing a nucleus of dilatation
160 within the half-space and an image nucleus outside the surface to satisfy the traction-free boundary condition at the ground
161 surface.

162 The displacement field can be expressed using the Galerkin vector formulation

163
$$2G\vec{u} = 2(1 - \gamma)\nabla^2\vec{F} - \nabla\nabla \cdot \vec{F}$$

164 where

165 G = shear modulus

166 γ = Poisson's ratio

167 \mathbf{F} = Galerkin vector, which is biharmonic.

168 For convenience, Mindlin used an alternative representation proposed by Westergaard:

169
$$2Gu_x = 2(1 - \gamma)\nabla^2X - \frac{\partial}{\partial x}\nabla \cdot \vec{F}$$

170
$$2Gu_y = 2(1 - \gamma)\nabla^2Y - \frac{\partial}{\partial y}\nabla \cdot \vec{F}$$

171
$$2Gu_z = 2(1 - \gamma)\nabla^2Z - \frac{\partial}{\partial z}\nabla \cdot \vec{F}$$

172 Mindlin and Cheng constructed the Galerkin vector function such that it satisfies both the spherical inclusion boundary
173 conditions and the free-surface boundary conditions of the half-space. The resulting function is expressed in cylindrical
174 coordinates as

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176
$$\vec{F} = \left(\frac{G\beta}{2\pi}\right) \vec{k} \left[\log(R_1' + z - c) + (1 - 4\gamma) \log(R_2' + z + c) + \frac{2(z+c)}{R_2'} - \frac{2c}{R_2'} \right]$$

177

178 where

179 R_1 is the distance from the field point to the center of the spherical inclusion $P(0,0,c)$,

180 R_2 is the distance from the mirror image inclusion located at $(0,0,-c)$,

181 a is the radius of the inclusion,

182 c is the depth of the inclusion center below the free surface,

183 and r, θ, z represent cylindrical coordinates.

184 Substituting this Galerkin vector into the displacement formulation yields the displacement field

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186
$$\vec{u} = \frac{a^3\beta}{3} \left[\frac{\overline{R_1}}{R_1^3} + \frac{(3-4\gamma)\overline{R_2}}{R_2^3} - \frac{6z(z+c)\overline{R_2}}{R_2^5} - \frac{2\vec{k}}{R_2^3} [(3-4\gamma)(z+c) - z] \right]$$

187 SURFACE DISPLACEMENT

188 At the ground surface ($z = 0$), the vertical displacement component becomes

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$$u_z = \frac{a^3\beta}{3} \left[-\frac{c}{R_1^3} + \frac{(3-4\gamma)c}{R_2^3} - \frac{6z(z+c)c}{R_2^5} - \frac{2}{R_2^3} [(3-4\gamma)(z+c) - z] \right]$$

191 which simplifies to

192
$$u_z|_{z=0} = -\frac{4(1-\gamma)ca^3\beta}{3R^3}$$

193 This expression describes the surface subsidence generated by a shrinking spherical inclusion embedded within a half-space.

194

195 SURFACE CURVATURE

196 The curvature of the surface deformation is obtained from the second derivative of the displacement field.

197 At the surface location directly above the inclusion ($r = 0$):

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199
$$\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} = 0$$

200 and

201
$$\frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial r^2} = \frac{4(1 - \gamma)a^3\beta}{c^4}$$

202 Because the first derivative is zero at this point, the curvature simplifies to

203 As the first order derivative of u_z with r equal to 0 at

204

205
$$\kappa = \frac{\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} u_z}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} u_z\right)^2\right]^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} u_z = \frac{4(1 - \gamma)a^3\beta}{c^4}$$

206

207 Substituting the volumetric strain relationship

208
$$\beta \approx 3\alpha$$

209 gives

210
$$\kappa = \frac{12(1 - \gamma)a^2\delta a}{c^4}$$

211 This result indicates that the curvature of the ground surface decreases with the fourth power of the depth of the inclusion,
212 demonstrating the rapid attenuation of subsidence effects with increasing depth.

213

214 **TRACK CURVATURE LIMIT**

215 For FRA Class 9 track, the allowable vertical track deviation is

216
$$\delta = \frac{3}{4}in$$

217 measured over a 62-ft chord.

218 This corresponds to an allowable curvature

219

220

$$\kappa = \frac{8\delta}{l^2}$$

221 which yields

222

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{7688 (ft)} = \frac{1}{1.46 (mile)}$$

223 **EXAMPLE CALCULATION**

224 Consider a spherical inclusion with

225 diameter = 20 ft

226 initial void ratio $e_0 = 1.1$

227 final void ratio $e_1 = 1.04$

228 giving

229

230

$$\delta e_0 = 0.06$$

231

232 From the volumetric strain relation

233

$$\beta = \frac{\delta e_0}{1 + e_0} = 0.029$$

234 and

235

$$\frac{\delta a}{a} = \frac{\beta}{3} \approx 0.01$$

236 As such

237

$$\delta a = 0.1 ft$$

238 Substituting into the curvature equation yields

239

$$c = 34.30 ft$$

240 Therefore, for a 20-ft diameter inclusion, if the center of the inclusion lies deeper than approximately 34 ft below the ground
241 surface, the resulting curvature will remain within the allowable limit specified for FRA Class 9 track.

242 **DISCUSSION**

243 Ground subsidence observed in regions affected by long-term groundwater extraction has raised concerns regarding its
244 potential impact on high-speed rail infrastructure. The analysis presented in this study indicates that track irregularity is
245 governed primarily by the curvature of differential subsidence rather than by the magnitude of total settlement itself.

246 In this study, localized soil consolidation was represented as a shrinking spherical inclusion embedded within an elastic half-
247 space. This modeling approach intentionally combines a shrinking inclusion as the source of subsidence with an elastic
248 medium representing the surrounding ground. The assumption is justified because the deformation produced by the shrinking
249 inclusion decays rapidly in a three-dimensional field. At sufficient distance from the source, the resulting deformation remains
250 small, and the linear elastic formulation provides a reasonable approximation of the physical mechanism while maintaining
251 adequate analytical accuracy. When the consolidation source is located close to the ground surface, however, the assumptions
252 underlying the present formulation may no longer hold strictly. In such cases, further refinement of the model may be required
253 to account for stronger near-field effects and potential nonlinear soil behavior.

254 The example presented in this study considered a single spherical shrinking inclusion. Because the governing equations are
255 based on linear elasticity, the principle of superposition applies. For consolidation sources with more complex geometries,
256 the subsiding region can be represented by a distribution of spherical inclusions with different sizes and locations. The
257 resulting displacement field can then be obtained by superimposing the contributions of these individual inclusions through
258 integration. This approach allows the analytical framework developed in this study to be extended to more general subsidence
259 configurations while retaining the clarity of the underlying physical interpretation.

260 The analysis also demonstrates that ground-surface curvature decreases with the fourth power of the depth of the consolidation
261 source. As a result, subsidence generated by deep consolidation layers can produce substantial cumulative settlement while
262 generating only minor surface curvature. Under such conditions, the influence on high-speed rail track geometry and
263 operational performance remains limited.

264 Although ground subsidence may still introduce practical challenges during construction, including surveying control,
265 earthwork quantity measurement, and acceptance criteria, particularly when combined with embankment settlement, these
266 issues fall outside the scope of the present study.

267 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

268 No data, models, or code were generated or used during the study.

269

270 **REFERENCES**

271 Mindlin, Raymond D. "Force at a Point in the Interior of a Semi-Infinite Solid." *Physics* 7, no. 5 (May 1936): 195–202.

- 272 Mindlin, Raymond D, and David H Cheng. “Nuclei of Strain in the Semi-Infinite Solid.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 21, 926
273 (1950).
- 274 Mindlin, Raymond D, and David H Cheng. “Thermoelastic Stress in the Semi-Infinite Solid.” *Journal of Applied Physics* 21,
275 931 (1950)
- 276 Kelvin, Lord, and William Thomson. *Mathematical and Physical Papers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.
- 277 Love, Augustus. “A Treatise on the Mathematical Theory of Elasticity,” CAMBRIDGE: AT THE UNIVERSITY PRESS,
278 1892.
- 279 Zhi-Chen, Wang, Song Ying, and Wang Jian-Xi. “Relation Between Track Irregularity of Speed-Increased Railway and
280 Dynamic Speed Limits Through Simulation.” *The Open Mechanical Engineering Journal* 8, no. 1 (September 16, 2014):
281 197–200.
- 282 Hung, C. F., and W. L. Hsu. “Influence of Long-Wavelength Track Irregularities on the Motion of a High-Speed Train.”
283 *Vehicle System Dynamics* 56, no. 1 (January 2, 2018): 95–112.
- 284 Federal Railroad Administration, *Track Safety Standards Compliance Manual*, January 1, 2002.
- 285 H. M. Westergaard, *Bull. Am. Math. Soc.* 41, 695 (1935)
- 286 Terzaghi, K. & Peck, R.B., 1967 – *Soil Mechanics in Engineering Practice*, 2nd edn. Wiley, New York.